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DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL ETHICS IN FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN LIBRARY, INFORMATION, AND ARCHIVAL STUDIES

The article explores the significance of professional ethics for future specialists in library, information, and archival studies within contemporary social and technological changes. It examines the relationship between professional ethics, information security, the preservation of intellectual integrity, and responsibility to society. The key approaches to developing students' ethical competence are outlined, including the integration of ethical disciplines into curricula and the application of practice-oriented teaching methods. Methodological approaches and diagnostic criteria for assessing ethical competence are proposed. Special attention is given to the challenges of digitalization, which necessitate adherence to information security standards and ethical conduct in data management.

Keywords: professional ethics; library, information and archival studies; ethical competence; information security; digitalization

У статті розглядається значущість професійної етики майбутніх фахівців бібліотечної, інформаційної та архівної справи в контексті сучасних суспільних і технологічних змін. Аналізується взаємозв'язок між професійною етикою, інформаційною безпекою, збереженням інтелектуальної доброчесності та відповідальністю перед суспільством. Окреслено основні підходи до формування етичної компетентності студентів, включаючи інтеграцію етичних дисциплін у навчальні програми та використання практико-орієнтованих методів навчання. Запропоновано методичні підходи та діагностичні критерії оцінювання рівня сформованості етичних компетенцій. Особлива увага приділена проблемам цифровізації, що вимагають дотримання норм інформаційної безпеки та етичної поведінки при роботі з даними.

Ключові слова: професійна етика; бібліотечна, інформаційна та архівна справа; етична компетентність; інформаційна безпека; цифровізація

The contemporary development of professional education necessitates a transformation in approaches to defining its content, requiring greater emphasis on the professional and ethical orientation of future specialists in library, information, and archival sciences within the market-driven paradigm of socio-economic development. Higher education in this field aims to cultivate professional competencies, the ability to work effectively with information resources, and adherence to the principles of objectivity, confidentiality, intellectual integrity, and professional responsibility.

Mastering creative approaches to addressing professional and real-life challenges based on ethical standards ensures the professional mobility of specialists.

The significance of professional ethics stems from dynamic social transformations that have led to an imbalance between material and spiritual values. This has underscored the need to integrate ethical norms into the professional activities of library and information specialists, who play a crucial role in the preservation, organization, and dissemination of information. Professional ethics is particularly vital in the context of digitalization, as professionals must uphold standards of information security, protect personal data, and prevent the spread of misinformation.

Adherence to ethical principles in the professional activities of librarians, archivists, and information analysts enhances trust in library and information institutions, reinforces the social responsibility of specialists, and establishes a stable system of moral and ethical values that align with contemporary challenges in the professional domain. The development of ethical competence among future professionals should be an integral component of their professional training. This objective is achieved through the integration of ethical disciplines into curricula, the application of practice-oriented teaching methods, and the cultivation of a responsible attitude toward professional activities.

Polish scholar G. Skorowski defines the ethos of a profession as the moral foundation of the practical behavior of members of a specific professional community within a given environment, shaped by its internal values and norms. At the same time, professional ethics possesses a distinct nature, as it is based not only on a description of existing moral practices but also on normative and evaluative approaches. It entails defining how professional activities should be structured in accordance with moral and ethical principles and establishing the corresponding standards of professional conduct [5].

Professor G. Vasyanovych conceptualizes professional ethics in three key aspects: as a set of norms that regulate the behavior of professionals in a given field; as the moral principles underpinning a specialist's activities; and as a mechanism for the ethical evaluation of professional conduct. The content of professional ethics is closely linked to universal moral norms, yet it also specifies and adapts them to particular professional contexts. This enables the development of responsible professional behavior oriented toward upholding high moral standards within the scope of professional practice [1].

The application of ethical standards in the field of library, information, and archival sciences is a crucial factor in ensuring professional responsibility, safeguarding the rights of information users, and maintaining public trust in library and information institutions. The development of ethical culture among future specialists should be an integral component of their professional training. This process entails not

only mastering relevant ethical norms but also fostering reflective thinking, which is essential for analyzing and resolving ethical dilemmas in professional practice.

The professional ethics of future specialists in library, information, and archival sciences plays a pivotal role in ensuring high-quality professional performance and fostering trust in library and information institutions. It establishes a framework of moral and ethical norms and principles that govern the behavior of professionals and their interactions with information users, colleagues, and society at large. Responsibility to society, adherence to professional ethics, and compliance with moral standards contribute to the social significance of the profession and its alignment with the evolving demands of the information society.

O. Lapuzina emphasizes that the formation of professional ethics among future specialists should be carried out within the framework of a moral and ethical paradigm of education, which requires a shift in approaches to the interaction between participants in the educational process. This transformation leads to the replacement of the traditional educational and disciplinary model with a personality-oriented system that promotes the democratization of the educational environment and the humanization of relationships between educators and students. Particular emphasis is placed on enhancing the moral and ethical competence of future professionals through the integration of innovative pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process [4].

The development of ethical culture among future specialists in library, information, and archival sciences is a fundamental prerequisite for their professional training. This process necessitates the establishment of methodological approaches and diagnostic criteria for assessing students' ethical competence. The implementation of personality-oriented teaching methods will facilitate the development of moral reflection, the ability to make ethically sound decisions, and a sense of responsibility in fulfilling professional duties within the field of information services.

Based on the aforementioned considerations, the formation of professional ethics among future specialists in library, information, and archival sciences can be approached through four key methodological frameworks: the comprehensive, competency-based, activity-based, and axiological approaches. The comprehensive approach integrates theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and moral convictions. The competency-based approach emphasizes the development of ethical competencies essential for professional practice. The activity-based approach focuses on engaging students in professional scenarios that simulate ethical dilemmas, while the axiological approach aims to cultivate a system of moral values centered on professional responsibility and social justice.

The assessment of professional ethics formation can be based on four diagnostic criteria: cognitive, motivational, behavioral, and reflective. The cognitive criterion

evaluates students' awareness of ethical norms and professional codes. The motivational criterion assesses their understanding of the significance of professional ethics and their sense of personal responsibility for adhering to moral principles. The behavioral criterion measures the ability to apply ethical knowledge in professional contexts, whereas the reflective criterion gauges students' capacity for critical self-analysis and their ability to adjust their professional conduct in alignment with moral and ethical standards.

From our perspective, the implementation of methodological approaches and diagnostic criteria in the educational process requires the introduction of specialized courses and modules on professional ethics, the integration of ethical issues into core disciplinary content, and the use of case-based methods to analyze real-world ethical dilemmas. Additionally, discussions, training sessions, and role-playing exercises serve as effective tools for fostering ethical awareness and decision-making skills. Problem-based learning technologies enable students to independently develop solutions to ethical challenges, thereby enhancing their critical thinking and moral reflection abilities. A crucial component of the educational process is the creation of professional decision-making scenarios that help students recognize the implications of their choices in real-world practice. Furthermore, the assessment of professional ethics proficiency can be conducted through questionnaires, testing, reflective essay analysis, and direct observation of students' behavior during educational practica and professional internships.

The professional ethics of future specialists in library, information, and archival sciences should be regarded as a comprehensive characteristic encompassing personal maturity, moral orientation, and the ability to perform professional duties responsibly. It should incorporate not only an understanding of professional norms and standards but also a profound awareness of the significance of ethical principles in daily professional practice. The ethical foundations established during professional training shape a specialist's moral consciousness and determine their ability to manage information, documents, and archival materials effectively and responsibly—an essential component of professional activities in library and information institutions.

In the process of educating specialists in these fields, it is essential to emphasize the development of moral competencies based on humane and tolerant approaches toward all stakeholders in the professional environment. This requires not only technical expertise in information management but also the ability to engage with colleagues, users, and other participants in the information space with mutual respect, trust, and ethical responsibility.

Thus, professional ethics constitutes an integral component of the training of future specialists, influencing not only their level of professionalism but also their

capacity to establish morally responsible and ethically balanced practices in an ever-evolving information landscape.

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КОРЕКЦІЯ ПРОБЛЕМНИХ ЗОН ПРИ ОНЛАЙН-НАВЧАННІ ВИЩОЇ МАТЕМАТИКИ

Указано на типові недоліки математичної підготовки першокурсників. Проаналізовано підходи до коригування проблемних зон і адаптації до вивчення вищої математики в умовах дистанційного навчання. Розглянуто форми організації коригуючої освітньої діяльності в синхронному і асинхронному режимах і проблеми реалізації та контролю результатів. Висвітлено проблеми і перспективи організації коригуючих заходів для забезпечення математичної компетентності.

Ключові слова: дистанційне навчання, вища математика, адаптація, наступність, мотивація.

Typical shortcomings of mathematical training of first-year students are indicated. Approaches to correcting problem areas and adapting to studying higher mathematics in distance learning conditions are analyzed. Forms of organization of corrective educational activities in synchronous and asynchronous modes and problems of implementation and control of results are considered. The problems and prospects of organizing corrective measures to ensure mathematical competence are highlighted.

Keywords: distance learning, higher mathematics, adaptation, continuity, motivation.